

D2.2

Database of trade volumes for biological resources and biobased products - Accompanying reading guide to the D2.2 Excel file

WR

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ABBREVIATIONS

OFMSW	Organic fraction of Municipal Solid Waste
ITC	International Trade Centre
FSC	Forest Stewardship Council
PRODCOM	PRODUCTION COMMUNAUTAIRE

1. Introduction

The development of sustainably produced and traded biobased products in the world can be measured via the impact indicator 'certification rate of traded intermediate and final biobased products at the global regional level in year x'. The objective of Task 2.2 is to find evidence for this indicator from current statistics departing from the eighteen biobased value chains as identified in Deliverable 2.1 (columns 1 to 4 in Table 1-1). The trade assessment has been carried out for ten out of these eighteen (see column 5 in Table 1-1).

The output of Task 2.2 is provided in the form of an Excel file (*D2.2_Database of trade volumes for biological resources and biobased products.xls*) with estimated trade flow data of (un)certified products in the selected value chains (Deliverable 2.2). This document should be seen as a short reading guide. The report starts with describing the approach in Chapter 2. Followed by explanation of the tables and figures presented in the Excel file (Chapter 3). It ends with an overview of main findings, conclusions and recommendations for further research (Chapter 4).

Table 1-1 Overview of the identified 18 most representative biobased value chains in D2.1, selected 10 value chains for assessment in D2.2

Biobased value chain	Subsector	Sector	Final score (from 0 to 100)	Global trade assessment in Task 2.2
Mulch film from organic waste	Agriculture	Plastics	89.09	YES
Prefabricated buildings from wood and wheat straw	Building envelope	Construction	76.75	YES
Adhesives from tall oil	Adhesives	Chemical	76.55	YES
Paper for graphical purpose from recycled paper	Graphical Paper	Pulp and paper	72.85	YES
Wooden bedroom furniture from Residues from sawn wood	Furniture	Woodworking	72.29	
Cases, boxes, crates, drums and similar packings from coniferous wood	Carpentry pieces	Woodworking	68.61	
Sacks and bags of polymers of ethylene from raw cane and beet sugar	Packaging	Plastics	65.37	YES
Tableware and kitchenware of plastic from maize	Consumer goods	Plastics	64.05	
Wooden frames for paintings, photographs, mirrors or similar object from ligneous materials (wheat straw + wood)	Manufacture articles	Woodworking	62.98	

Biobased value chain	Subsector	Sector	Final score (from 0 to 100)	Global trade assessment in Task 2.2
Doors, frames and thresholds subflooring from hemp	Wooden structures	Construction	60.77	
Solvent for cleaning from maize	Solvents	Chemical	60.65	
Builder's joinery and Carpentry for window from coniferous wood	Interior Construction	Construction	59.26	YES
Table linen of flax	Furniture	Textile	58.75	
Napkins from Bagasse sugar cane fibre	Sanitary Paper	Pulp and paper	56.79	YES
Cartons, boxes and cases of corrugated paper from coniferous wood	Packaging	Pulp and paper	55.85	
Lubricants from vegetable oil	Lubricants	Chemical	54.56	YES
T-shirts, singlets and vests, knitted or crocheted from Cotton, carded or combed	Clothing	Textile	52.54	YES
Textile wicks, conveyor belts or belting from Greasy wool not carded or combed	Industry	Textile	51.78	YES

Source: based on Task 2.1 and Deliverable 2.1 in SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project

2. Approach

2.1 Production and trade data sources

PRODCOM, COMEXT/COMTRADE (both Eurostat) and FAOSTAT (FAO) databases have been used to map products of the ten selected value chains (Table 1-1) in terms of EU production, EU imports, EU exports. Product mapping is according to the product coding protocol of the International Standard Classification System (Figure 1).

Figure 1 International Standard Classification System

Moreover, the five main importing countries to the EU of each specific products have been identified. It should be noted that in general these top five countries represent 90% to 100% of total imports to the EU for the analysed products.

The data analyses dealt with several shortcomings in the used public data sources on:

- Production and trade data hardly entails detail on if a product is fossil-based or biobased (neither in volumes nor in prices).
- Production and trade data don't differentiate if a product is certified or uncertified (neither in volumes nor in prices).
- The allocation of the intermediate (biological) feedstock over uses, i.e. if it is used as input for chemical materials, textile, construction material, biofuels or another product, is not published at such a micro/value chain level. In general statistics are strong on the supply side but rather weak on the uses side. To bridge the gap, conversion rates between (i) biological feedstock and intermediate biobased product, and (ii) intermediate biobased product and final biobased product have been collected. They are used as proxies in order to estimate how much of a specific feedstock is needed to produce an x amount of the biobased final product in the identified value chains.

Expert knowledge for estimating values on identified gaps was gathered from:

- *Deliverable 2.1*: conversion rates, biobased shares, import dependence of biobased products (depending on the (sub)sector).
- *H2020 BioMonitor project*¹: conversion rates between biological feedstock and biobased chemical products, and biobased shares of chemical products.
- *Grey literature and expert knowledge*².

Deliverable 2.1 has screened and identified the most relevant schemes for industrial biobased systems, also considering the coverage of different feedstock types and sector of prominence in the market. It resulted in eleven shortlisted sustainability certification schemes and ecolabels. Task 2.2

¹ Sturm et al, 2022.

² European Forest Institute has provided some woody conversion rates (oral information)

has further investigated if data sources on the selected certification schemes/labels provide useful real trade data or alternatively provide a (proxy) indicator for estimating certification shares in trade.

2.2 Deriving certification rates in value chains

In general, the biobased value chains identified in Deliverable 2.1 consist of three product stages:

- *Biological feedstock*, being input for the
- *Intermediate material product*, being input material for the
- *Final material product*

Trade can take place at each of the three stages in the value chain, which means that certification rates must be considered at each stage. Therefore, the five regions with highest export flows (in volumes) to the EU have been prioritized for each product stage in the selected value chains (from COMEXT and COMTRADE). Note that the aggregate volume of the 5 regions makes 90-95% of total EU imports of the given product.

Certified biological feedstock within the value chain

The ITC standard map¹ has been proven to be a useful source for estimating certification rates of biological feedstock types produced in world regions for 14 voluntary certification schemes². The countries that produce certified feedstock are compared to the countries that export the most to the EU. If a country matches, the certification rate is used as proxy for the biological feedstock that enters the EU in a given value chain (see Table 1-1); if there is no match, the certification rate is considered to be zero for that given country. This approach has been assessed as follows:

- The % certified sugar cane land is reported per region and per scheme (Bonsucro, Organic, Fairtrade and Proterra). If a country is not mentioned the % certified sugar cane land is assumed to be zero. If the sugar cane land in a region is certified for more than one scheme, the scheme with the highest rate is taken. See the Sacks and Bags value chain.
- The % certified cotton land is reported per region and per scheme (Better Cotton). If a country is not mentioned, the % certified cotton land is assumed to be zero. See the t-shirts value chain.
- The % certified oilseed land is reported per region and per scheme (RSPO). If a country is not mentioned, the % certified oilseed land is assumed to be zero. See the Lubricant value chain.
- The % certified forestry land is reported per region and per scheme (FSC and PEFC). If a country is not mentioned, the % certified forestry land is assumed to be zero. If the forestry

¹ <https://standardsmap.org/en/trends>.

² The ITC standard map presents data on selected commodities from 14 voluntary sustainability standards: 4C Services, Better Cotton Initiative, BONSUCRO, Cotton made in Africa, Fairtrade International, Forest Stewardship Council (FSC), GLOBAL.G.A.P., IFOAM - Organics International, Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification Schemes (PEFC), ProTerra Foundation, Rainforest Alliance, Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil (RSPO), Round Table on Responsible Soy (RTRS), and UTZ.

land in a region is certified for two schemes, the scheme with the highest rate is taken. See the Adhesives value chain, Graphical paper value chain and Window frame value chain.

It is hard to find numbers on percentage certified wool (used in the Wicks and Belts value chain) and straw (used in the Prefabricated buildings value chain) produced in world regions.

Certified intermediate and final biobased products within the value chain

Websites assigned to the main international certification schemes, like ISCC Plus¹, RSB² and Better Biomass³, publish lists with all certificates (issued by the certification body) and statements of conformity. Cases of expired or withdrawn certificates are also published. Unfortunately, the websites and related reports don't provide data on aspects like (i) share of the certified company number producing a specific biobased product in total company number producing that specific product (in a region); (ii) production/market size of the companies that is certified compared to production/size of all companies. Further details on the knowledge gaps are described in Annex 1.

3. Findings

Deliverable 2.2 has the form of an Excel sheet, named *D2.2_Database of trade volumes for biological resources and biobased products.xls*. This Excel file contains 10 sheets, each representing production and trade data details for the selected value chains as shown in Table 1-1:

- *MulchFilm_OFMSW*: Mulch film from organic fraction of municipal solid waste
- *PrefabrBuildings_Straw*: Prefabricated buildings from wood and wheat straw
- *Adhesives_Talloil*: Adhesives from tall oil
- *PaperGraphic_RecycledPaper*: Paper for graphical purpose from recycled paper
- *SacksBagaPackaging_Ethylene*: Sacks and bags of polymers of ethylene from raw cane and beet sugar
- *Windows_Coniferous*: Builder's joinery and Carpentry for window from coniferous wood
- *Napkins_Paper_Pulp*: Napkins from sugarcane bagasse fibre
- *Lubricants_VegetableOils*: Lubricants from vegetable oil
- *TextileShirts_Cotton*: T-shirts, singlets and vests, knitted or crocheted from Cotton, carded or combed
- *WicksBelts_Wool*: Textile wicks, conveyor belts or belting from Greasy wool not carded or combed

Each sheet consists of a same set of tables, figures and infographics with data for the whole EU in the period 2010-2021. When opening the file, the reader can select a year in the orange cell via a drop-down list, see example for the value chain 'Adhesives from tall oil' (Figure 2).

¹ <https://www.iscc-system.org/certification/certificate-database/all-certificates/>

² <https://rsb.org/certification/rsb-certificates/>

³ <https://betterbiomass.nl/en/certificate-holders/>

Value chain:	Adhesives from tall oil via tall oil resins				
Select year =>	2020				

Figure 2 Select the year via the drop-down list. Data in tables and infographic are automatically refreshed.

In principle, the variety of possible (mature and emerging) biobased value chains is endless. There exists no database that reports on market size at the level of a biobased value chain, even not at the level of intermediate and final biobased products within the value chain. Table 3-1 contains a set of performance indicators that are obtained from e.g. Deliverable 2.1, PRODCOM, BioMonitor, experts, and grey literature and needed to estimate the EU market size and EU trade flows for the different product stages identified in the selected biobased value chains (see tables 3.2 to 3.6).

Table 3-1 Performance indicators (estimates) for the example value chain 'Adhesives from tall oil'

Value	Description
15%	Actual biobased share of Adhesives produced in EU (CE-2; see D2.1)
100%	Actual biobased share of tall oil resins produced in EU (BioMonitor; own estimate)
92%	Actual % of biobased Adhesives produced in EU (CT-3; see D2.1) *
3%	Actual % of tall oil imported to EU (calculated from PRODCOM; cf. CT-2; see D2.1)
97%	Actual % of tall oil produced in EU (calculated from PRODCOM; cf. reciprocal CT-2; see D2.1)
2.00	Conversion rate between kg tall oil required for 1 kg tall oil resins (cvr-1)
0.33	Conversion rate between kg tall oil resins for 1 kg Adhesives (cvr-2)
0.66	Conversion rate between kg tall oil for 1 kg Adhesives (derived from $cvr-1 * cvr-2$; cvr-3)

Source: own calculations based on EUROSTAT statistics, BioMonitor project, Deliverable 2.1, grey literature, information technical experts.

Table 3-2 shows the market volumes – in terms of production, imports, exports and apparent use – for the 3 stages within this value chain (biological feedstock, intermediate product, final product). Data reported is directly derived from statistics as these don't disaggregate between biobased and fossil-based products. Table 3-3 depicts estimated market data for the biobased component of the value chain. These have been calculated by connecting conversion rates, biobased shares and import shares (provided in Table 3-1) to numbers in Table 3-2.

Table 3-2 EU market data for products within the total (fossil-based and biobased) value chain - for the example value chain 'Adhesives from tall oil', 2020

Product in value chain	Production	Imports	Exports	Use (apparent)	Import-%
Tall oil	6559	2263	2278	6544	25.6%
Tall oil resins	451	158	7	601	26%
Adhesives	149	22	77	94	12.8%

Source: PRODCOM, COMEXT; own calculations

Table 3-3 Estimated EU market size (1000t) of biobased value chain - for the example value chain 'Adhesives from tall oil', 2020

Product in value chain	Production*	Imports	Exports	Use (apparent)**	Import-%
Tall oil	14.3	0.4	0.0	14.8	3%
Tall oil resins	5	2	0	7	26%
Adhesives	22	2	0	24	8%

Source: Calculations based on conversion rates, biobased shares, import shares (see performance indicators)

* Estimated production of actual biobased adhesives= total adhesives * biobased % = 149 *15% = 22 1000t (2020)

** Estimated tall oil resins used as input for producing the actual volume of biobased adhesives = biobased adhesives production * conversion factor = 22 * .33 = 7 1000t (2020)

** Estimated tall oil needed as input for tall oil resins needed to produce actual volumes of biobased adhesives = tall oil resins * conversion factor = 7 * 2 = 14 1000t (2020)

Table 3-4 shows the import of the biological feedstock (tall oil) used in the Adhesives value chain from the 5 top importing regions to the EU, and the associated certification rates per region. Certification rates are considered to be linked as well to FSC/PEFC certified forestry land in the given countries. Similar tables are available for the other value chains in the Excel sheet *D2.2_Database of trade volumes for biological resources and biobased products.xls*.

Table 3-4 Import of tall oil (biological) feedstock in the Adhesive biobased value chain from 5 key countries to EU (1000k) and estimated certification rate of trade

	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Total imports of tall oil	2658	2645	2572	2682	2428	2263	2309
- % certified forestry area	39.9%	40.9%	41.0%	41.1%	42.4%	42.4%	41.8%
<i>Main importers to EU:</i>							
<i>Brazil</i>	1345	1330	1299	1375	1152	1101	1289
- % certified *	39.6%	39.6%	39.6%	39.6%	39.6%	39.6%	39.6%
<i>United States</i>	479	495	486	475	511	464	403
- % certified*	61.0%	61.0%	61.0%	61.0%	61.0%	61.0%	61.0%
<i>Uruguay</i>	346	400	418	460	477	456	413
- % certified*	46.0%	46.0%	46.0%	46.0%	46.0%	46.0%	46.0%
<i>Chile</i>	296	243	248	236	197	181	173
- % certified*	6.1%	6.1%	6.1%	6.1%	6.1%	6.1%	6.1%
<i>Canada</i>	60	58	42	42	23	19	19
- % certified*	10.9%	10.9%	10.9%	10.9%	10.9%	10.9%	10.9%

Source: own calculations from COMEXT, PRODCOM and IPC standard map; * % certified land is kept the same over the period as time series are not available.

Table 3-5 shows the import of tall oil resins (intermediate biobased product) in the Adhesives value chain from the 5 top importing regions to the EU, and the associated certification rates per region. Certification rates are considered to be linked as well to FSC/PEFC certified forestry land in the given countries. Similar tables are available for the other value chains in the Excel sheet *D2.2_Database of trade volumes for biological resources and biobased products.xls*.

Table 3-5 Import of tall oil resins in the Adhesives biobased value chain from 5 key countries to EU (1000k) and estimated certification rate of trade

	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Total import of tall oil resins	106	175	169	121	110	158	166
- % certified forestry area	10.5%	10.6%	10.3%	9.9%	10.3%	16.9%	15.6%
<i>Main importers to EU:</i>							
<i>United States</i>	89	153	137	87	75	104	113
- % certified	10.9%	10.9%	10.9%	10.9%	10.9%	10.9%	10.9%
<i>Russia</i>	16	17	29	31	32	40	41
- % certified	6.1%	6.1%	6.1%	6.1%	6.1%	6.1%	6.1%
<i>Belarus (Belorussia)</i>	0	0	0	0	1	12	11
- % certified	99.0%	99.0%	99.0%	99.0%	99.0%	99.0%	99.0%
<i>United Kingdom</i>	1	1	1	1	0	1	0
- % certified	51.0%	51.0%	51.0%	51.0%	51.0%	51.0%	51.0%
<i>Türkiye</i>	0	0	1	1	2	1	1
- % certified	19.5%	19.5%	19.5%	19.5%	19.5%	19.5%	19.5%

Source: own calculations from COMEXT, PRODCOM and IPC standard map; * % certified land is kept the same over the period as time series are not available.

Table 3-6 shows the import of adhesives (final product) in the Adhesives value chain from the 5 top importing regions to the EU, and the associated certification rates per region. Certification rates for adhesives - thus at the level of the final product in the value chain - are hard to find (see also Annex 1). Similar tables are available for the other value chains in the Excel sheet *D2.2_Database of trade volumes for biological resources and biobased products.xls*.

Table 3-6 Import of Adhesives (final product) in the Adhesives biobased value chain from 5 key countries to EU (1000k) and estimated certification rate of trade

	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Total import of tall oil resins	9	11	12	14	20	22	28
- % certified forestry area	n/a						
<i>Main importers to EU:</i>							
China	2	1	2	3	5	5	2
- % certified	n/a						
Ukraine	0	0	0	0	5	8	16
- % certified	n/a						
United Kingdom	2	2	2	4	4	4	3
- % certified	n/a						
Egypt	2	2	2	1	2	2	2
- % certified	n/a						
Türkiye	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
- % certified	n/a						

Source: COMEXT, PRODCOM; n/a not available

Error! Reference source not found. visualize the role of the main importers of biological, intermediate and final products in the Adhesives value chain to the EU in the period 2010-2021. Similar figures are available for the other value chains in the Excel sheet *D2.2_Database of trade volumes for biological resources and biobased products.xls*.

Figure 3 Import (1000t) of Tall oil from main import countries to EU, 2010-2021

Figure 4 Import (1000t) of Tall oil resins from main import countries to EU, 2010-2021

Figure 5 Import (1000t) of Adhesives from main import countries to EU, 2010-2021

Finally, Figure 6 shows an infographic on certified trade in stages of the value chain. The numbers are automatically updated based on the selected year.

Figure 6 Infographic on certified trade in stages of the value chain -- for the example value chain 'Adhesives from tall oil'

4. Conclusions and recommendation

4.1 Conclusions

Main findings on data availability regarding the measuring of certification rate in trade of biobased value chains analysed in Task 2.2 (see Table 1-1):

- *Primary dedicated feedstock*: the share of certified trade has been approximated by the share of certified land for a specific biological feedstock in the region that exports the biological feedstock to the EU. The ITC standard map provides data on percentage certified land in world regions that is allocated to respectively vegetable oil crops, , sugar cane land, and cotton land.
- *Primary residue feedstock*: information is missing on the share of certified EU production of straw in total EU straw production. Note that straw is not imported to the EU.
- *Secondary residue feedstock*: the share of certificated imported tall oil has been derived from the share of FSC/PEFC certified forestry land in the regions that export to the EU.
- *Tertiary residue feedstock*: the share of certificated imported recyclable paper has been derived from the share of certified forestry land in the regions that export to the EU. information is missing on the share of certified EU production and trade of OFMSW.
- *Intermediate and Final biobased product*: the share of certified production and trade is hard to find, neither from the main international certification schemes (ISCC Plus, RSB and Better Biomass), nor from the literature.

To summarize:

- Certified trade of biological feedstock used in the biobased value chain analysed in Task 2.2 can mostly be approximated by data of the ITC standards map on certified land use of a specific feedstock at regional level. Exceptions are wool and straw (primary residue) for which there is lack of information.
- Data gaps occur especially downstream the value chain regarding certification rates of intermediate and final biobased products that are produced in EU or traded between EU and non-EU. The publicly available data is insufficient for this purpose. In order to get a better understanding into the inventory of certified products from sectors such as plastics, paper and pulp, chemicals and construction the certification bodies need to better report the breakdown of certificates per sector/product and region in their annual publications. There also is a need for interviews with key companies in each sector or the certification bodies to gather more understanding about the market of voluntary certifications as the voluntary nature is also a key limitation to improving reporting capabilities.

More details on the attempt to get a better understanding of certified products in the material industries are described in Annex 1.

4.2 Recommendations

The development of sustainable biobased production and trade in the world can be measured via the impact indicator 'certification rate of traded intermediate and final biobased products at the global regional level in year x'. However, it was deemed difficult to find good evidence for this indicator from current

statistics, or from websites and annual reports of scheme providers. In general, certification providers only publish the list of companies that have valid, withdrawn or fake certificates, but there is no annual integral monitoring of real certified production and trade for intermediate and final biobased production (in volume terms) at a regional level.

In the short term, the pilot audits in WP4 of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project could help address this data gap issue. Pilots are planned within the project between company stakeholders engaged in production and trade of biobased products versus owners of certification schemes/labels. If possible, some pilot biobased companies can be asked to provide estimates on the share of certified biobased production in total biobased production.

In the longer term, public data sources (such as Eurostat, FAO) should also start collecting market data on sustainable production in sectors at a regional level in order to establish a good monitoring system. This takes a long time as it is an expensive and administrative-heavy procedure, with commitment of national statistical offices in the EU and worldwide. It may also be difficult to collect data on a regular basis due to the mostly voluntary character of certification schemes; companies certified in the one year can decide not to get re-certified another year, which could hamper the efforts of gaining a solid sample of market data.

Annex 1 Getting insight in the size of certified biobased production

Current limitations to the certification labels for biobased products are as follows. The ISCC PLUS certification system merges intermediate and final products in their overall reporting of certifications. The ISCC and RSB schemes allow for Mass balance approaches to their bio-based accounting methods. This means it is not possible from documentation available to discern the amount of certificates granted which are based on the percentage of product certified versus a part of the product that is certified material.

The four certification schemes ISCC PLUS, RSB Advanced Products, Better Biomass and EU ECO Label are varied in scope of products certified and regions. EU ECO Label for example is solely for EU products and so is not useful for certifications of products imported into the EU. Better Biomass is also predominantly EU based. ISCC PLUS and RSB are global certifiers but the existing documentation and available register of certifications does not have a way for certifications to be filtered by country or per sector.

The inability to clearly filter certifications based by sector makes it impossible currently to get an overview of certifications for companies and link it to other trade data to create estimations on percentages of biobased products with certification versus non certified or versus no biobased segments of the market.

For sectors such as construction the use of certifications is extremely difficult to navigate. There is an abundance of self-reported claims of biobased products but a lack of third party certification. There is also no standard criteria for what is certified, i.e. the building company, the producer or the specific products. Furthermore the range of products from wood which is naturally biobased or for products with biobased substitutes replacing cement, metals or plastics has be disentangled and further investigated to understand the biobased economy in this sector.

At present the plastics sector offers the most coherent overview of biobased certifications¹. With some estimates made on the percentage share of the market that is biobased and how it is segregated by global regions. This is also linked with the knowledge of existing certifications and what products they cover. The other sectors such as chemicals, textiles and construction need further sector efforts to map what products are certified by which standards and how big a share of the biobased market it constitutes.

Key limitations to mapping the certified biobased products in the bioeconomy:

- Poor database labelling of certification websites.
- ISCC Plus & RSB Certifications mix mass balance methods with segregated methods.
- Intermediate and final products mixed in certification accounting.
- Certificates don't clearly distinguish what product is to which sector.
- Certification standards don't all create annual reports.
- Certifications report on awarded certificates instead of currently valid ones.
- Products may not renew certificates and creating and maintaining a record of data becomes inconsistent.
- Linking certificates to companies and products they trade with the EU and from what regions is unclear.

Table A-4-1 represents an estimate of calculating what percentage of EU registered companies have biobased certifications to estimate the share of the biobased market that is certified.

¹ [EURATEX Facts & Key Figures 2022](#)

Table A-4-1 EU Ecolabel certified labels numbers and as share of registered enterprises in the EU

Sector	Region	Certification	Certified labels (number)	Certified products (number)	Total enterprises (number)	% of labels as part of total enterprises
Textile	EU	EU Ecolabel	86(2023)	20294(2023)	142,934(2022)	0.06%
Paper and Pulp	EU	EU Ecolabel	357(2023)	9250(2023)	679(2021)	52.50%
Chemicals	EU	EU Ecolabel	1405(2023)	45137(2023)	28000(2020)	5.02%
Construction	EU	EU Ecolabel	n/a	7096(2023)	n/a	n/a

n/a not available

The figures of total enterprises are from sector reports on trade statistics¹²³. The percentages represent the certified labels issued per sector as a percentage of the total companies stated in the sector reports which derive their data from Eurostat. This figure is estimated based on the assumption that certified labels which comprise a group of products that can be certified are issued to unique individual companies with no overlap. This assumes one company only attains one certified label for its products. This however could vastly differ in reality as a single company or brand could have multiple certified labels but this cannot be checked from available public data or that the certified labels have been grouped into the correct sector. For instance pulp and paper certified labels comprise graphic paper, printed paper, stationary paper and paper certified bag products, tissue paper and tissue products. Chemical certified labels is comprised of cosmetic products, dishwasher detergents, industrial and institutional dishwasher detergents, laundry detergents, lubricants etc. The labelling of these products is not standardised by the label and could belong to different sectors. This figure is to demonstrate the limitations of giving an estimate of certified products for one certification body and how these uncertainties become worse the larger the scope.

Table A-4-2 Certification labels (number) broken down by region

Labels for group of products	EU	World-wide	Asia	South America	North America	Oceania/Australia
ISCC PLUS	254	199	22	52	7	14
RSB Global Advanced Products	14	n/a	6	n/a	1	2
EU Ecolabel	1848	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
Better Biomass	164	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a

Table A-4-2 shows the extent the four certification schemes focused on can be broken down by their regional distribution. These were acquired from the registers on the website of each certification. This is filtered by labels of certifications not individual product certificates. The labels are also filtered by validity. The table results show the regional distribution but it is not possible to see the brake up of labels by product or company to map

¹ [EURATEX Facts & Key Figures 2022](#)

² [Key-Statistics-2021-Final.pdf \(cepi.org\)](#)

³ [the-european-chemical-industry-facts-and-figures-2020.pdf \(francechimie.fr\)](#)

them to sectors. It is also difficult to get market reports on products from global regions as opposed to country specific.

These estimate figures and identified limitations highlight the difficulties with identifying the percentage of final biobased products that are certified and from what regions they enter the EU. The publicly available data is insufficient for this purpose. In order to get a better understanding into the inventory of certified products from sectors such as plastics, paper and pulp, chemicals and construction the certification bodies need to better report the breakdown of certificates per sector/product and region in their annual publications. There also is a need for interviews with key companies in each sector or the certification bodies to gather more understanding about the market of voluntary certifications as the voluntary nature is also a key limitation to improving reporting capabilities.

About SUSTCERT4BIOBASED

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED is an EU funded (Horizon Europe) project aiming at defining and promoting the adoption of effective and robust sustainability certification schemes and business-to-business labels for industrial biobased systems to support tracing the sustainability (environmental, social, economic) of biobased products along the value chains and trades within the EU and globally for responsible production and consumption. This objective is realised by the development of a monitoring system, mapping of the current situation in global trade flows of biological resources and biobased products, and feasibility assessment from the adoption of certification schemes and labels considering actual economic as well as internalized environmental and social costs and benefits. The results of the project are leveraged to provide recommendations to four key target groups: policy makers, sustainability system community, industrial biobased value chain actors, and regional bioeconomy stakeholders. These ambitions are addressed by a strong, well-balanced and multi-disciplinary consortium comprised of 5 complementary partners. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED thereby supports the development of harmonized system requirements, continuous improvement of sustainability certification schemes and labels and contributes towards establishing a circular, climate-neutral and sustainable biobased industry.

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